

Questionnaire for ”A Quantitative Exploration of the 9-Factor Theory: Distribution of Leadership Roles between the Scrum Master and the Agile Team”

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1 Comments for the Reader

This questionnaire was used for a study on quantitatively measuring the 9-Factor Theory on the Scrum Master roles, which helps to measure leadership in agile teams. For more information on the 9 leadership roles of a Scrum Master, please refer to Spiegler et al. (2019)*.

Next to the Likert Scale reaching from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree', we provided an additional option 'Don't Know / Not Applicable' which is not enumerated here.

Furthermore, we did not name the 9 Factors in the original survey. That means, items were not linked to any factor/ leadership role but put in randomized order in order to avoid response bias. To allow practitioners using our questionnaire in real organizational settings, we mention the 9 factors in this survey and link the items to the respective leadership roles in this questionnaire. Yet, we advise when using this survey for scientific purpose, to not mention the factors but to put all items in randomized order.

The survey is divided into two separate questionnaires: one examining which leadership roles the Scrum Master plays, one to enumerate which leadership roles the agile team performs. First, participants have to state if they are a Scrum Master or a member of the agile team. They then receive the questionnaire related to their specific role.

The first questionnaire is used for Scrum Masters.

The second questionnaire is used for team members.

*Spiegler, S. V., Heinecke, C., Wagner, S. (2019, May). Leadership gap in agile teams: how teams and scrum masters mature. In International Conference on Agile Software Development (pp. 37-52). Springer, Cham.

2 Questionnaire for the Scrum Master

General Question

What is the focus topic of your team? You may cross more than one if applicable.

- Software Development
- Hardware Development
- Mechanical Engineering
- Software and Hardware Development
- IT
- HR
- Purchasing
- Other:

How many months have you been working with your current team colleagues?

0-2	3-5	6-8	9-11	≥ 11
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How many months has your current team been working in an agile manner?

0-2	3-5	6-8	9-11	≥ 11
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How many months have you been playing the Scrum Master role?

0-2	3-5	6-8	9-11	≥ 11
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Questionnaire 1: Scrum Master Activities

Imagine your daily activities as a Scrum Master. I (Scrum Master) would describe myself as doing the following activities:

Method Champion

strongly agree →
← strongly disagree

- Teaches the Scrum method and practices.
- Supports formulating tasks.
- Schedules Scrum meetings.
- Facilitates Scrum meetings.
- Stimulates discussion on how to adapt the Scrum method....
- Brings new methods to the team.
- Organizes team events.

Disciplinizer on Equal Terms

- Supports team members to obey the rules the team agreed on.
- Helps team members to focus on relevant topics.
- Monitors tasks/progress.
- Makes sure team members attend meetings.
- Communicates on a par/on eye level.

Coach

- Observes team members.
- Uncovers which kind of behavior is missing in a team to improve teamwork.
- Provides feedback.
- Builds team trust.
- Helps team to find out what they wish to change.
- Helps team to find out how to change.
- Brings developing conflicts to the surface.

Change Agent

- Serves as a role model.
- Convinces project teams of the agile way of working.

Influences decisions at higher level that support the team to work in an agile way.....	☐				
Acquires needed resources.....	☐				
Convinces management of the agile way of working.....	☐				
Helps team members to accept failure and learn from it.....	☐				
Helps team members to be open towards results.....	☐				
Helicopter					
Possesses the ability to see the bigger picture.....	☐				
Knows who possesses the skill for a certain task.....	☐				
Identifies links between individuals and tasks from different technical expertise or domains towards a common goal.....	☐				
Includes relevant stakeholders.....	☐				
Structures work.....	☐				
Be quick in handing over the work to another professional of another expertise.....	☐				
Moderator					
Moderates discussions.....	☐				
Builds a bridge between different perspectives and domains..	☐				
Helps to develop understanding each other properly.....	☐				
Helps to develop tolerance towards different point of views...	☐				
Supports shared decision-making.....	☐				
Networker					
Connects team members with relevant stakeholders, e.g. managers and/or experts, from within the organization.....	☐				
Connects team members with relevant experts, e.g. from neighbouring departments or projects.....	☐				
Connects team members with relevant stakeholders, e.g. managers and/or experts, from outside the organization.....	☐				
Motivates team members to network with others.....	☐				
Knowledge Enabler					
Realizes which kind of knowledge the team needs (e.g. expert information, methodological skills).....	☐				
Supports team members to acquire new knowledge.....	☐				
Visualizes information.....	☐				

Motivates team members to attend training.	☐				
Motivates team members to go to conferences.	☐				
Schedules knowledge exchange meetings.	☐				
Promotes iterative learning (e.g. learning from mistakes, fosters learning-by-doing).	☐				
Urges team to take time for learning.	☐				
Fosters learning from each other.	☐				
Protector					
Shelters team from inappropriate requests from the Product Owner, managers, disciplinary leaders or other departments.	☐				
Protects team from re-prioritization.	☐				
Shelters team from management and Product Owner intervening in daily business.	☐				
Shelters team from management over-ruling decisions the team had come up with.	☐				
Protects team from re-staffing.	☐				

Questionnaire 2: Scrum Team Activities

Imagine the daily activities of the Scrum team. I (Scrum Master) would describe the Scrum team as doing the following activities:

Method Champion

strongly agree →
← strongly disagree

- Teaches the Scrum method and practices.
- Supports formulating tasks.
- Schedules Scrum meetings.
- Facilitates Scrum meetings.
- Stimulates discussion on how to adapt the Scrum method.
- Brings new methods to the team.
- Organizes team events.

Disciplinizer on Equal Terms

- Supports team members to obey the rules the team agreed on.
- Helps team members to focus on relevant topics.
- Monitors tasks/progress.
- Makes sure team members attend meetings.
- Communicates on a par/on eye level.

Coach

- Observes team members.
- Uncovers which kind of behavior is missing in a team to improve teamwork.
- Provides feedback.
- Builds team trust.
- Helps team to find out what they wish to change.
- Helps team to find out how to change.
- Brings developing conflicts to the surface.

Change Agent

- Serves as a role model.
- Convinces project teams of the agile way of working.

Influences decisions at higher level that support the team to work in an agile way.....	☐				
Acquires needed resources.....	☐				
Convinces management of the agile way of working.....	☐				
Helps team members to accept failure and learn from it.....	☐				
Helps team members to be open towards results.....	☐				
Helicopter					
Possesses the ability to see the bigger picture.....	☐				
Knows who possesses the skill for a certain task.....	☐				
Identifies links between individuals and tasks from different technical expertise or domains towards a common goal.....	☐				
Includes relevant stakeholders.....	☐				
Structures work.....	☐				
Be quick in handing over the work to another professional of another expertise.....	☐				
Moderator					
Moderates discussions.....	☐				
Builds a bridge between different perspectives and domains..	☐				
Helps to develop understanding each other properly.....	☐				
Helps to develop tolerance towards different point of views...	☐				
Supports shared decision-making.....	☐				
Networker					
Connects team members with relevant stakeholders, e.g. managers and/or experts, from within the organization.....	☐				
Connects team members with relevant experts, e.g. from neighbouring departments or projects.....	☐				
Connects team members with relevant stakeholders, e.g. managers and/or experts, from outside the organization.....	☐				
Motivates team members to network with others.....	☐				
Knowledge Enabler					
Realizes which kind of knowledge the team needs (e.g. expert information, methodological skills).....	☐				
Supports team members to acquire new knowledge.....	☐				
Visualizes information.....	☐				

Motivates team members to attend training.	☐				
Motivates team members to go to conferences.	☐				
Schedules knowledge exchange meetings.	☐				
Promotes iterative learning (e.g. learning from mistakes, fosters learning-by-doing).	☐				
Urges team to take time for learning.	☐				
Fosters learning from each other.	☐				
Protector					
Shelters team from inappropriate requests from the Product Owner, managers, disciplinary leaders or other departments.	☐				
Protects team from re-prioritization.	☐				
Shelters team from management and Product Owner intervening in daily business.	☐				
Shelters team from management over-ruling decisions the team had come up with.	☐				
Protects team from re-staffing.	☐				
Thank you for participating in this survey!					

3 Questionnaire for the Team Members

General Questions

What is the focus topic of your team? You may cross more than one if applicable.

- Software Development
- Hardware Development
- Mechanical Engineering
- Software and Hardware Development
- IT
- HR
- Purchasing
- Other

How many months have you been working with your current team colleagues?

0-1	1-2	3-4	5-8	≥ 9
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How many months has your current team been working in an agile manner?

0-1	1-2	3-4	5-8	≥ 9
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How many team members are you?

3-4	5-6	7-8	9-10	≥ 10
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Questionnaire 1: Scrum Team Activities

Imagine your daily activities as a team. I (team member) would describe myself or one or more other team colleagues as doing the following activities:

Method Champion

strongly agree →
← strongly disagree

- Teaches the Scrum method and practices.
- Supports formulating tasks.
- Schedules Scrum meetings.
- Facilitates Scrum meetings.
- Stimulates discussion on how to adapt the Scrum method.
- Brings new methods to the team.
- Organizes team events.

Disciplinizer on Equal Terms

- Supports team members to obey the rules the team agreed on.
- Helps team members to focus on relevant topics.
- Monitors tasks/progress.
- Makes sure team members attend meetings.
- Communicates on a par/on eye level.

Coach

- Observes team members.
- Uncovers which kind of behavior is missing in a team to improve teamwork.
- Provides feedback.
- Builds team trust.
- Helps team to find out what they wish to change.
- Helps team to find out how to change.
- Brings developing conflicts to the surface.

Change Agent

- Serves as a role model.
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Influences decisions at higher level that support the team to work in an agile way.....	☐				
Acquires needed resources.....	☐				
Convinces management of the agile way of working.....	☐				
Helps team members to accept failure and learn from it.....	☐				
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Helicopter					
Possesses the ability to see the bigger picture.....	☐				
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Identifies links between individuals and tasks from different technical expertise or domains towards a common goal.....	☐				
Includes relevant stakeholders.....	☐				
Structures work.....	☐				
Be quick in handing over the work to another professional of another expertise.....	☐				
Moderator					
Moderates discussions.....	☐				
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Helps to develop understanding each other properly.....	☐				
Helps to develop tolerance towards different point of views...	☐				
Supports shared decision-making.....	☐				
Networker					
Connects team members with relevant stakeholders, e.g. managers and/or experts, from within the organization.....	☐				
Connects team members with relevant experts, e.g. from neighbouring departments or projects.....	☐				
Connects team members with relevant stakeholders, e.g. managers and/or experts, from outside the organization.....	☐				
Motivates team members to network with others.....	☐				
Knowledge Enabler					
Realizes which kind of knowledge the team needs (e.g. expert information, methodological skills).....	☐				
Supports team members to acquire new knowledge.....	☐				
Visualizes information.....	☐				

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Shelters team from management and Product Owner intervening in daily business.	☐				
Shelters team from management over-ruling decisions the team had come up with.	☐				
Protects team from re-staffing.	☐				

Questionnaire 2: Scrum Master Activities

Imagine the daily activities of your Scrum Master. I (team member) would describe my Scrum Master as doing the following activities:

Method Champion

strongly agree →
← strongly disagree

Teaches the Scrum method and practices.	☐				
Supports formulating tasks.	☐				
Schedules Scrum meetings.	☐				
Facilitates Scrum meetings.	☐				
Stimulates discussion on how to adapt the Scrum method.	☐				
Brings new methods to the team.	☐				
Organizes team events.	☐				

Disciplinizer on Equal Terms

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Protects team from re-staffing.	☐				
Thank you for participating in this survey!					